

Properties of Natural Fibres for Composite Materials

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SUMMARY

Natural fibres, particularly those which form a waste material from other industries, are of interest to manufacturers as an easily sourced material, from which a composite material could be produced. The current work suggests that a cheap composite with commensurate mechanical properties could be produced based on oil palm fibre.

Keywords: natural fibres, mechanical properties, Weibull statistics

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre composites, whether based on a bio-derived polymer matrix or more conventional resin systems, are of interest for the production of comparatively low or even negative carbon footprint materials. When considering the ‘green credentials’ of bio-derived composites it is therefore important to consider the source of the fibres used and the processing required to produce a useful composite. Nettle[1] or carrot [2], when grown explicitly to provide fibres for composite materials can be viewed as primary source materials since the fibres required are extracted leaving excess material as waste. Alternatively, wood flour or sawdust, which are waste materials from a primary process have been used as fillers or to make “synthetic wood” e.g. [3] but even this relatively mature area is still of interest, particularly in the context of using recycled or post-primary use polymers [4]. At longer reinforcement length scales flax, jute and other such natural fibres have been investigated and reviewed e.g. [5].

The fibres used in the current work are waste from palm oil production and as such are readily available and hence worthy of investigation as possible reinforcing materials. In time the questions that must be answered are:

1. Can a viable composite material be produced from as-received fibres or do the fibres require processing?
2. If they require processing, then how does this affect the economic and environmental properties of the composite?

The current work, which is a limited, proof-of-concept study, comprises a microstructural and mechanical characterisation of the fibres and demonstrates their potential for use in the production of composite materials.

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MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF OIL PALM FIBRE

Fibres have been examined using both optical and scanning electron microscopy. For optical microscopy, samples were attached to slides, attempting to minimise stretching of the fibres whilst ensuring that they lay flat and relatively untwisted. An environmental scanning electron microscope (with a variable pressure chamber, Hitachi S3200N) was used in order to overcome issues with the non-conducting nature of natural fibres. Whilst it is generally accepted that the resolution when in environmental mode is comparatively poor, it is still possible to produce acceptable images and useful data.

One of the key issues with natural fibres is the lack of uniformity in the basic material. The associated irregularity in the cross-section presents a particular challenge when carrying out optical microscopy. It is difficult to focus on a surface that is both rounded and of non-uniform cross-section and hence the edges are rarely both in focus at the same time. Other features include varying cross-section (Figure 1a); branching or splitting of the fibre (Figure 1b) and variations in the internal microstructure (Figure 1c and d). Note that Figure 1c represents a cut end, whilst Figure 1d is a fracture surface generated from a tensile test. Despite their differences in origin, the difference in the surface morphology is more to do with variation in the fibre structure than with specimen production: the central region of the specimen in Figure 1d shows evidence of much larger tubules, which are not artefacts associated with the fibre fracture.

Figure 1 – Optical (a and b) and scanning electron (c and d) micrographs of oil palm truck fibres

TENSILE TESTING OF SINGLE FIBRES: METHODOLOGY

To carry out tensile testing, single fibre samples have been glued to window cards of 50 mm internal length (as shown in Figure 2). The width (c.f. Figure 1a) of the fibre was measured at intervals along the length. It has been assumed, following precedent [6], that the specimen has a circular cross-section, and therefore the measured width has been taken to be the diameter. Whilst it can be seen in Figures 1c and 1d that this is not quite the case, it can also be seen that this is not an unreasonable approximation. The average diameter was used to determine a nominal cross-sectional area for the calculation of stress. After testing, a more accurate stress was determined by using the cross-section measured nearest to the failure location.

Figure 2 – Specimen orientation

An Instron 6025 (5500R) testing machine was used, with a 100 N load cell, running Bluehill 2 (Instron proprietary software). The grips were pneumatic. The sample was loaded to failure under displacement control at a rate of 0.5 mm/min and the load-displacement graph recorded. In the first instance a batch of 30 specimens was prepared for testing and from this batch five were chosen at random for cyclic testing. These samples were loaded until past yielding, unloaded and reloaded for a total of 3 cycles. Cyclic testing was conducted in order to assess the change, if any, on the modulus, since this provides an indication of rate dependency of the tensile behaviour. Since there was some indication that this might be the case (discussed further, below), further cyclic testing was carried out on another five samples and continued to a total of 20 cycles for each specimen.

TENSILE TESTING OF SINGLE FIBRES: RESULTS

Stress-Strain Behaviour

Examples of typical stress-strain results are presented in Figure 3. It should be noted that a) the stresses are based on the pre-test fibre diameter closest to the eventual fracture of the fibre and b) the strains presented are derived from cross-head displacement and are therefore indicative rather than absolute. However, in reference to the properties of the fibres the effect of the compliance of the machine is expected to be minimal. As can be seen in Figure 3, the fibres are capable of achieving reasonable stresses-to-failure (the average failure stress is 60 MPa, with a standard deviation of 20 MPa, from a set of 25 samples) but of more interest is the strain to failure of these fibres which is typically of the order of 8 $\epsilon\%$, with some samples going beyond 16 $\epsilon\%$, albeit with some, rarely, failing at strains of only 2-3 $\epsilon\%$. With comparison to flax [7, 8], the stress is an order of magnitude lower, but the strain to failure is approximately a factor of four greater. Together with the non-linearity of the force-displacement response, this much greater strain to failure of the oil palm fibre suggests that these fibres can provide a respectable energy absorption capability.

Figure 3 – Comparison of some stress-nominal strain plots for single fibre tests

Figure 3 is also of interest in terms of comparing the range of behaviours seen in testing. As well as the variation in failure strength and strain mentioned above, it can be seen that the elastic region shows some variation as well. This figure shows the extremes found in the batch of fibres which range from 1.1 GPa (specimen 10) to 2.9 GPa (specimen 9).

Strength Data

The failure stresses of the 25 samples loaded to failure were derived from both the average cross-sectional area and the cross-sectional area closest to the failure location. The results are presented in Table 1. It might be expected that when we consider strengths calculated from the diameter closest to the specimen failure, then an increase would be observed when compared to the average diameter of the specimen. In fact whilst this occurs in 60 % of the samples tested, in the remainder, failure occurs at a cross-section of greater than average area. Considering Figure 1, then, it appears that larger cross-sections are likely to contain more stress raising defects, although in this context a reduction in cross-section is usually more significant. Even so, this increase is comparatively modest; the increase in the average strength is only 8 MPa or ~13%.

Table 1 – Diameter and strength data for the fibres tested loaded to failure.

	diameter (μm)		load at failure (N)	failure strength (MPa)	
	at failure (1)	average (2)		(1)	(2)
1	338	392	7.5	83	62
2	490	439	15.6	83	103
3	483	473	9.8	53	56
4	373	398	8.8	80	71
5	401	512	13.6	108	66
6	503	438	13.1	66	87
7	442	410	4.8	32	37
8	436	524	10.3	69	48
9	423	402	15.2	108	120
10	515	517	4.4	21	21
12	534	511	12.1	54	59
13	525	479	10.1	47	56
15	365	464	4.2	40	25
17	407	540	9.9	76	43
18	577	715	13.7	52	34
19	715	588	13.2	33	49
20	259	328	4.4	84	52
21	506	536	18.0	89	80
22	549	476	8.3	35	46
23	419	473	10.0	72	57
25	361	396	10.3	101	84
26	330	377	7.5	87	67
28	430	376	9.8	68	88
29	285	328	3.6	56	42
30	356	507	9.4	95	47
Avg.	441	464	10	68	60
s.d	101	86	3.9	25	24

Energy Absorption Capacity

Considering the load-displacement data (and remembering that the displacement is actually that of the crosshead, with an assumption that in this case it may reasonably be

taken as that of the specimen) it is possible to calculate the energy absorbed per sample. Of the 25 samples that were tested in tension to failure, some showed evidence of progressive failure i.e. one that was not immediately catastrophic on reaching the peak load, but neither could it be described as a “graceful failure”. This type of failure is attributed to a fibre that is in fact a smaller or larger group of fibrils that fail sequentially, but this remains to be confirmed as part of future work. In the current work, in order to assess the energy absorbing capacity of the fibres, for just 10 specimens have been analysed and these data are presented in Table 2. These all displayed the type of stress-strain response, presented in Figure 3, with catastrophic failure at the peak load. On average the energy absorbed per sample is 35 mJ although the standard deviation is large: 20 mJ. More useful however is to consider the energy absorbed per m³, which is on average 4.5 MJ/m³ with a standard deviation of 2.7 MJ/m³. Density has been determined by an Archimedean methodology. The oil palm fibres were found to have a density of ~0.8 g/cm³ and this gives an energy absorption capability of 5.6 kJ/kg. A review of natural fibres [9] includes a comparison of densities and this value is very low compared with flax (1.4 g/cm³) and jute (1.46 g/cm³). Coir was found to have the lowest density at 1.25 g/cm³. In the present study, samples of glass and carbon fibre were tested at the same time and found to have densities of 1.7 and 2.7 g/cm³ respectively and this compares well with the literature, giving confidence in the technique. However, given the highly porous nature of the natural fibres it is likely that a technique such as helium pycnometry will give a more realistic assessment of the density, as well as giving an indication of the level of closed and open porosity. Hence, it can be seen that a modest loading could act to both reduce the density of the material and increase the energy absorbing capability, depending of course on the matrix.

Table 2 – Energy absorption

	Energy absorbed mJ	Sample volume mm ³	Energy absorbed per unit volume MJ/m ³
Test 1	17	6.0	2.82
Test 2	31	7.6	4.06
Test 3	54	8.8	6.13
Test 4	37	6.2	5.91
Test 5	39	10.3	3.81
Test 6	61	7.5	8.07
Test 7	8	6.6	1.21
Test 8	39	10.8	3.57
Test 9	57	6.4	8.91
Test 10	5	10.5	0.44
Average	35	8.1	4.49
s.d.	20	1.9	2.76

This stress data has then been analysed by Weibull methods. Whilst the fibres cannot be described as brittle, the fit to a two parameter Weibull model is good, which suggests

that this is a useful way of modelling the properties of these fibres. Figure 4 compares the Weibull plot derived from the strength data calculated using the average fibre diameter with that derived from the diameter at failure. In both cases the Weibull modulus is 3, which is to be expected from a non-uniform material and may reasonably be compared to flax. Untreated green flax has also been found to have a Weibull modulus of about 2 for fibres of length 10 mm [6]. Samples of 5 mm have a Weibull modulus of 3-4, whilst retting leads to Weibull moduli of 3 and 4 at the respective lengths. Surface treatments have been shown to improve the Weibull moduli, but even the best treatments only give a Weibull modulus of 6-7. The good fit to a Weibull model here suggests that the oil palm fibres fail due to a single mode; this is perhaps at odds with the stress data but suggests that further research is required.

Figure 4 – Weibull plot comparing strength data derived from both fibre average diameter and the diameter of the fibre at failure

Cyclic Response

As mentioned in the methodology, some samples were tested cyclically (i.e. loaded and unloaded several times). In the first instance 5 samples were tested for 3 cycles each. Results from one of these tests is shown in Figure 5. Here the stiffening observed is comparatively modest, although the modulus is one of the highest observed: the modulus for the first cycle is 4.6 GPa and for the third 4.8 GPa. The general trend observed is towards a slight stiffening and hence further testing with a larger number of cycles was undertaken. Figure 6 shows data from one of the 20 cycle specimens. For clarity the data has been presented in terms of the first, second and twentieth cycles. In this case the effect of stiffening is much more marked with the modulus increasing from 1.6 GPa to 2.4 GPa by the twentieth cycle, although it will be observed that much of the

stiffening occurs by the second cycle (modulus reaches 2.2 GPa). Stiffening of fibres is not uncommon and is usually associated with the reorientation of molecules. For example, in the case of Kevlar fibres, stiffening has been attributed to unkinking of misaligned portions of the molecules [10]. What has not been determined at this time is whether the stiffening of these natural fibres is reversible. For example, the study on Kevlar fibres [10] was able to show that the stiffening was reversible over time, with full recovery taking approximately 1 week. This was attributed to variations in molecular alignment between the surface and core of the fibre, leading to strains when the covalent bonds between molecules are stretched. Hence, it is argued that there is a 'restoring stress' which causes the molecules that have been unkinked when the fibre is stretched to resume their distorted conformation once the applied stress is removed. However, such recovery is not seen in all fibres. Silks in general [11] and spider-silk(s) [12] in particular, which are formed from combinations of different proteins (where different combinations can lead to very different mechanical properties) and which might be expected to show similar recovery to Kevlar, is generally treated as a 'one-shot' material. (Single cycle testing has shown that the mechanical properties of spider silks are strain rate dependent [13], with stiffening of the fibres. Recovery in spider silk has been observed[14], but this is a very different mechanism (referred to as super contraction) and requires the silk to become wet. Such treatment returns the fibre to its original condition i.e with excellent properties for one cycle (but with no evidence of stiffening).

Noticing the hysteresis between the loading and unloading curves (particularly the 2nd cycle) in Figure 5, it is not unreasonable to predict some form of recovery in these natural fibres, although given the variation in the fibre structure (implicit from the range observed in the properties and explicit from Figure 1) it is unlikely that full recovery would be achieved.

Figure 5 – Example of a stress-strain plot for a three cycle test

Figure 6 – Example of a stress-strain plot for a twenty cycle test, where the first, second and twentieth cycle are compared.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Palm oil fibres have been shown to have interesting, albeit modest, mechanical properties. Given the low density of the fibres, these fibres can be considered as an excellent candidate as a filler. Other properties, such as the relatively large strains-to-failure, and therefore the potential for absorbing comparatively large quantities of energy, suggest that continued investigation is warranted. In particular cyclic testing has shown stiffening of the fibre which suggests strain rate dependency and this is an area that would be of interest for further testing. Given the hysteresis observed there is also a need to evaluate the extent and rate of recovery, if any, associated with the fibres.

The current work has not considered the physico-chemical properties of the fibre surfaces. Whilst this is not necessary to simply create a composite or filled polymer, an understanding of the surface properties combined with the polymer chemistry can be used to model the fibre-matrix interaction and hence the properties of the composite. Further, if the interface between a suitable matrix and the fibre can be tailored to achieve the optimum strength (without degrading the fibres), a cheap composite with reasonable energy absorbing capacity could be produced.

References

1. Bodros, E. and C. Baley, *Study of the tensile properties of stinging nettle fibres (Urtica dioica)*. Materials Letters, 2008. **62**(14): p. 2147-2149.
2. Hepworth, D. and E. Whale, *Biocomposite Material in US Patent*. 2008.
3. S. N. Maiti, K.S., *Influence of wood flour on the mechanical properties of polyethylene*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 1986. **32**(3): p. 4285-4289.
4. Huda, M.S., et al., *Wood-fiber-reinforced poly(lactic acid) composites: Evaluation of the physicomechanical and morphological properties*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2006. **102**(5): p. 4856-4869.
5. Mohanty, A.K., M. Misra, and G. Hinrichsen, *Biofibres, biodegradable polymers and biocomposites: An overview*. Macromolecular Materials and Engineering, 2000. **276**(3-4): p. 1-24.
6. Zafeiropoulos, N.E. and C.A. Baillie, *A study of the effect of surface treatments on the tensile strength of flax fibres: Part II. Application of Weibull statistics*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**(2): p. 629-638.
7. Bos, H.L., M.J.A. Van den Oever, and O. Peters, *Tensile and compressive properties of flax fibres for natural fibre reinforced composites*. Journal of Materials Science, 2002. **37**(8): p. 1683-1692.
8. Zafeiropoulos, N.E., G.G. Dijon, and C.A. Baillie, *A study of the effect of surface treatments on the tensile strength of flax fibres: Part I. Application of Gaussian statistics*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**(2): p. 621-628.
9. Wambua, P., J. Ivens, and I. Verpoest, *Natural fibres: can they replace glass in fibre reinforced plastics?* Composites Science and Technology, 2003. **63**(9): p. 1259-1264.
10. Ganczakowski, H.L., et al., *The Behavior of Kevlar Fiber Epoxy Laminates under Static and Fatigue Loading .2. Modeling*. Composites Science and Technology, 1990. **37**(4): p. 371-392.
11. Altman, G.H., et al., *Silk-based biomaterials*. Biomaterials, 2003. **24**(3): p. 401-416.
12. Hayashi, C.Y., N.H. Shipley, and R.V. Lewis, *Hypotheses that correlate the sequence, structure, and mechanical properties of spider silk proteins*. International Journal of Biological Macromolecules, 1999. **24**(2-3): p. 271-275.
13. Gosline, J.M., et al., *The mechanical design of spider silks: From fibroin sequence to mechanical function*. Journal of Experimental Biology, 1999. **202**(23): p. 3295-3303.
14. Elices, M., et al., *Recovery in spider silk fibers*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2004. **92**(6): p. 3537-3541.